

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO DETERMINING THE TECHNICAL ACCEPTABILITY OF INNOVATIVE CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS

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Abstract

The article examines the current problem of assessing the technical acceptability of innovative construction products, which plays a key role in ensuring their safety, reliability and compliance with modern standards. Particular attention to the analysis of the specifics of innovative materials and structures, which require the development of new methodological approaches for the objective assessment of their characteristics.

The paper considers the criteria for technical acceptability, which include physical and mechanical properties, energy efficiency, environmental friendliness and compliance with the regulatory framework. Methodological recommendations based on a step-by-step approach are proposed. The practical significance of the work lies in the formation of a comprehensive approach that allows developers, engineers and certification bodies to optimize the process of evaluating new construction solutions. The implementation of these methodological approaches will contribute to efficient use of resources, minimizing risks and increasing consumer confidence in innovative construction products.

Keywords: innovations, technical acceptability, enterprise, construction, environmental friendliness.

Assessment of the technical acceptability of innovative construction products is an important stage of the innovative development of investment and construction projects, since technical barriers (the need for certification or other confirmation of product compliance with environmental, technical, operational and other requirements) can significantly reduce the effectiveness of investments in innovation or even become an obstacle to project implementation.

The rapid evolution of construction technologies has introduced a number of innovative products that may change the industry in the future. From advanced materials to the most modern construction methods, these innovations offer such potential benefits as im-

proved parameters (strength, performance, fire resistance, etc.) economic efficiency and environmental friendliness. However, the assessment of innovative construction products requires different approaches compared to materials, products and structures that been used in construction for a long time.

In the construction industry, technical acceptance assessment is a fundamental process for ensuring that materials and products meet the required performance, safety and regulatory standards, but it differs significantly when evaluating innovative construction products. Understanding the differences is crucial for successfully integrating new materials and technologies into construction practices while maintaining the integrity and safety of the built environment (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Features of technical acceptance assessment of innovative construction products (developed by the author)

In construction, technical acceptance assessment of products is crucial for ensuring compliance with the required standards for performance, safety.

Building materials, products and structures that used to construct buildings and structures for many years, such as concrete, steel and brick, used in construction for decades or even centuries. Their properties and characteristics are well known, documented, and standardized, and tested against established standards and building codes that have been refined over decades. For example, the compressive strength of concrete or the tensile strength of steel are assessed using standardized test methods that are well known and understood by all construction professionals.

As a result, the technical evaluation of such products usually based on established standards and codes that have been refined over time, perhaps to more stringent requirements. Standards are developed and tested to ensure that traditional materials meet established requirements. Reliance on established standards simplifies the evaluation process because the technical parameters of these materials are predictable and are evaluated using standard methods.

Innovative building products, such as advanced 3D printed composites, fundamentally new building materials, products and structures, or intelligent building technologies, are often implemented using new technologies and methods that do not yet have established standards or regulatory guidance. The novelty of these products means that existing standards may not be fully applicable or may need to be adapted. Therefore, the assessment of innovative products requires the development of new criteria and test methods or the adaptation and re-use of existing ones to take into account the unique characteristics of the innovations and their potential impacts. The assessment of traditional materials, products and structures by using well-known methods, which makes the assessment process simpler and more understandable. However, innovative products in construction may lack extensive data, may be produced in a single copy or in small batches, which does not allow for statistical confirmation of individual parameters and leads to uncertainty in the quantitative assessment of performance parameters, reliability, etc. This requires additional resources for data collection, testing and verification. Innovative products may require the creation of new evaluation methods, separate laboratory equipment, or require complex integration, which requires careful comparison, comparison and coordination with existing evaluation systems. Materials, products and structures that traditionally often used in construction only benefit from standardization, which simplifies evaluation and norming using established procedures and data. On the contrary, innovative products often require individual approaches due to new characteristics and standards that just being created and developed, which may involve the development of new evaluation methods, test protocols and integration strategies. This may serve as an additional barrier to innovation of products on the market and their widespread distribution

The effectiveness (environmental, economic, technical and even marketing) of traditional construc-

tion products is usually predicted on the basis of extensive historical data and empirical evidence of their use in the construction of various objects, sales on the market, manufacturers, operating conditions, etc. Empirical data from numerous objects throughout the life cycle of buildings and structures provide a reliable basis for the evaluation of such materials, products and structures. For example, the durability and load-bearing capacity of different brands of ceramic bricks are well known, and deviations from the expected characteristics rarely occur. Or the compressive strength of concrete can be reliably measured and evaluated using standardized test methods. Predictable and standardized procedures simplify the evaluation process, since the characteristics of construction products are largely consistent across different regulatory documents, they have already used repeatedly in different projects and programs, which allows for direct evaluations based on previous indicators and established test protocols.

The performance of innovative products may be less predictable due to their innovative nature. Unlike traditional materials, which have extensive empirical data, innovative products may lack a long history of use and a history of evaluating performance under a variety of conditions, under a variety of external and internal factors. As a result, the evaluation of these products often involves extensive testing, modeling, and validation to understand their performance characteristics and long-term behavior under different conditions.

The testing procedures for traditional building products are well-established and standardized. These procedures include methods for assessing properties such as load-bearing capacity, strength, fire resistance, and thermal insulation, often standardized with clear protocols. The focus of the evaluation is usually on confirming that the product meets these established standards and meets expectations. Because the test protocols are widely accepted and understood, the evaluation process is more routine and less complex.

The evaluation of innovative products generally requires more comprehensive and individual testing compared to traditional products. This may include prototype testing, simulations, and pilot projects to assess performance characteristics such as durability, safety, and compatibility. The goal is to confirm that the innovative product meets or exceeds the technical acceptability requirements necessary for its intended application.

One of the main challenges in evaluating innovative construction products is the lack of historical performance data. Traditional materials benefit from extensive empirical evidence and well-established experience, which provides a reliable basis for estimating costs and expected performance. In contrast, innovative products may have limited or no historical data, making it difficult to accurately predict their performance and cost. Innovative construction products may incorporate new construction technologies or materials that require different methods of integration into existing systems. Evaluating the cost and feasibility of integrating these products can be challenging, as it involves understanding how the new products interact with traditional materials and construction methods.

Innovative products often introduce new technologies or methods whose long-term performance is not fully known. This uncertainty can affect various aspects of the assessment, including the product's durability, maintenance requirements, and overall impact on the project. Without proven operational experience, decision makers must rely on pilot projects, simulations, or expert judgment to assess performance and make informed judgments.

Traditional products are typically subject to well-defined regulatory requirements and building codes. These codes are designed to ensure safety and reliability and are typically applied consistently across the industry. Assessments primarily involve verifying that the product meets the stated regulatory requirements, or that the products comply with existing codes and standards, which provides a clear basis for assessing technical acceptability.

The regulatory framework for traditional products is stable and well-defined, facilitating compliance and assessment. Innovative products are subject to evolving regulations, which can complicate the assessment and standardization processes as new standards are developed and implemented.

Regulatory frameworks for innovative products are often under development or change as new technologies emerge, and the regulatory framework for innovative products often evolves with new technologies. Assessors may need to work closely with regulators to develop appropriate standards and guidance for new products. This process may include negotiating with regulators, conducting additional research and providing evidence of product safety and efficacy, negotiating with regulators, and adapting to new regulatory requirements.

The regulatory environment for innovative construction products often changes as new technologies emerge. Standards and codes may not yet be fully developed or may require adaptation to take into account the unique characteristics of innovative products. This can complicate the assessment process as assessors must navigate changing regulations and ensure that products meet current standards.

Due to the innovative nature of innovative products, there is often a higher level of risk associated with their use. Assessors must carefully assess potential risks and implement risk management strategies to address any uncertainties. This may include conducting failure mode analyses, assessing potential environmental impacts and developing contingency plans.

The assessment of the technical acceptability of construction products involves different approaches depending on whether the product is traditional or innovative. Traditional products benefit from established standards, expected performance and routine testing, which simplify the assessment process. In contrast, innovative products require a more flexible and adaptable approach that includes new testing methods, evolving regulatory frameworks and extensive validation to address uncertainties and ensure reliability. Understanding these differences is essential for integrating new technologies into construction practices while maintaining standards of safety, performance and compliance.

The assessment of technical acceptability for traditional and innovative construction products involves different approaches, shaped by the nature of the products being assessed. Traditional products benefit from established standards, expected performance and conventional testing procedures, which make their assessment relatively straightforward. In contrast, innovative products require a more flexible and adaptive approach to assessment, incorporating new testing methods, evolving regulatory frameworks and comprehensive risk assessment. Recognizing these differences is essential for successfully integrating innovative technologies into construction practices, while ensuring that all products meet the required performance, safety and regulatory standards.

The assessment of technical acceptability of construction materials, products and structures is crucial for ensuring their compliance with project specifications, standards and regulatory requirements.

The general methodology for assessing the technical acceptability of building materials, products and structures within investment and construction projects consists of the following steps:

Step 1. Determining the main requirements and evaluation criteria, which may be technical requirements and requirements for the functional characteristics of the building product based on project specifications, industry standards and regulatory guidelines and additional key evaluation parameters important for the developer, such as strength, durability, safety, environmental impact and compatibility with other materials.

Step 2. Collecting documentation and specifications - obtaining detailed documentation from the manufacturer, including technical characteristics of the material, product or structure, technical data and inspection certificates, determining whether the product complies with relevant industry standards, building codes and regulatory requirements.

Step 3. Initial screening - conducting an initial review of the construction product documentation to ensure that it meets the specified requirements and standards, that the material, product or structure has the necessary certificates and approvals from Ukrainian or international standardization organizations or regulatory authorities.

Step 4. Technical testing. Selecting test methods based on the type of product and evaluation parameters. Such testing may include laboratory testing, field testing, or both. Also at this stage, it is possible to perform tests to assess the acceptability of the product (performance, durability and safety). Such tests, which may include tests for strength, fire resistance, moisture resistance or other relevant properties and analyzing test results to determine whether the product meets the required technical and performance criteria.

Step 5. Assessing the product's compatibility with other materials and systems used in the construction project. This includes checking for problems related to adhesion, thermal expansion or chemical reactions, conducting compatibility testing and, if necessary, conducting additional tests to assess how the product interacts with other materials and systems.

Step 6. Assessing the manufacturer's quality, its manufacturing processes - the manufacturer's quality

control and assurance processes to ensure consistent product quality and manufacturing facilities, if applicable, manufacturing facilities to ensure that they meet industry standards and are capable of producing products that meet specifications.

Step 7. Consult with experts, engineers or consultants to obtain professional opinion on the technical acceptability of the product, familiarize yourself with practical examples of its use or examples of previous projects where the product was used to assess its performance in real conditions.

Step 8. Document the results of the evaluation, including test results, compatibility assessments and expert opinions, based on the evaluations to obtain recommendations on whether the product is technically acceptable, needs modifications or should be rejected.

Step 9. Discuss the results with project stakeholders, including project managers, designers and contractors, as well as building material manufacturers (competitors) and, based on the evaluation and discussion, make decisions on acceptance, modification or rejection of the product.

Step 10. Monitor and review after acceptance of the product throughout the life cycle of the property or at least the duration of the construction project to ensure that it meets expectations. It is also recommended to collect feedback from stakeholders on the performance of the product and resolve any issues that arise.

The assessment of the technical acceptability of construction products involves a comprehensive approach that includes defining criteria, conducting tests, assessing compatibility and consulting experts. By following the steps outlined, stakeholders can ensure that construction products meet the required standards and are effective in their intended applications, which helps to minimize the risks associated with the use of new construction products.

Conclusions. The assessment and regulation of innovative construction products is significantly different from traditional materials due to factors such as novelty, data limitations, integration complexity and changing regulations. While traditional products benefit from established standards, expected performance and conventional methods, innovative products require individual approaches to address their unique characteristics and problems. Understanding these features is essential for effective project planning and the successful integration of new technologies into construction practices. By adapting assessment and regulation methods to take into account the characteristics of innovative products, stakeholders can better manage risks, optimize resources and drive progress in the construction industry.

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